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Research Article

THE USE OF MICROBIAL TRANSGLUTAMINASES AS A NEW PROMISING DIRECTION IN COMPLEX TREATMENT OF WOUNDS

Yeskova A.Yu.¹, Petrenko A.D.², Dydykin S.S.¹, Vasil'ev Y.L.¹, Fomochkina I.I.³, Shaymardanova
L.R.³, Makalish T.P.³, Bessalova Ye.Yu.³

¹I.M. Sechenov First Moscow State Medical University, Department of Plastic Surgery, Department of Operative
Surgery and Surgical Anatomy, Moscow, Russia

²V.I.Vernadsky Crimean Federal University, Tavricheskaya Academy, Institute of Foreign Languages, Simferopol,
Russia

³V.I.Vernadsky Crimean Federal University, Medical Academy named after S.I. Georgievsky, Department of
pathological physiology, Department of Normal Anatomy, Central Research Laboratory, Simferopol, Russia

For correspondence: Yeskova Alexandrina Yu., clinical resident of the Department of Plastic Surgery,
I.M. Sechenov First Moscow State Medical University, Moscow, Russia, 2502aleksandrina.es@gmail.com

Abstract:

The purpose was to analyse the scientific sources studying the structure and functions of that enzyme in various living species, as well as the possibilities of its use in industry and medicine for wounds healing.

Wounds healing are an urgent medical problem, where closure of wounds (ridges convergence) by means of stitches and adhesives is of primary importance, as well as the use of wound healing medicines. Despite the abundance and variety of drugs available on the pharmaceutical market, the local therapy of wound defects of various aetiologies, the desired degree of reparative effect has not been achieved yet. The existing standards of pharmacotherapy of wounds do not satisfy both the effectiveness of treatment and the cost of achieving the final result. In surgery, at the initial stages of the wound process, simple antiseptics and wound-healing ointments are used ("Solcoseryl" and "Metuluracil" are the leaders).

The modern level of development of science allowed us to study the wound healing process at the molecular level. In this aspect, the development and implementation of biocompatible materials is an important trend in modern biopharmaceuticals. At present, much attention is paid to the mechanisms of the organization of wound contents and tissue matrix reforming. Transglutaminases (TG enzymes) (serum and tissue) that are capable of forming proteolysis-resistant cross-linking between extracellular matrix proteins are involved in these processes. Drugs of human serum TG in Russia, like all blood products, are produced and used in a limited way. TG of mammals and humans are autoantigens and may be associated with the pathogenesis of certain diseases. At the same time, inexpensive MTGs are widely used in the industry as safe technological agents. TG of microbial origin, unlike oligomeric TGs of mammals and humans, are small single-chain proteins, their activity does not depend on the concentration of calcium ions, they are stable at storage and, at the same time, they are characterized by rapid biodegradation.

The idea of creating a new remedy (ointment) containing microbial TG in combination with traditional phytopreparations and active components that affect various targets of the pathological process in tissue damage, and determined the purpose and objectives of our study. At the same time, the mechanisms of reparation should be further investigated in a series of clinical trials.

Key words: *transglutaminase, wounds healing, pathogenesis, enzyme preparations, collagen synthesis.*

Corresponding author:**Yeskova A.Yu,**

I.M. Sechenov First Moscow State Medical University,

Department of Plastic Surgery, Department of Operative Surgery and Surgical A.

Moscow, Russia

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

A deep cut wound is one of the most common injuries in accidents and still remain a global public health problem. Despite many successes in wound therapy, there is still a need to search and develop new medicines for their local treatment [12, 13, 16, 26, 37]. The search for new inexpensive in the production of biotechnological medicines intended to correct the wound process and treat wounds, seems to us relevant and timely. One of the promising directions is the use of transglutaminases - enzymes, which form strong chemical bonds, in cells and in molecules of intercellular substance. Transglutaminases of microbial origin are of greatest practical interest for the expansion of the possibilities of surgery and veterinary medicine in the field of wound healing. The modern level of development of science allowed us to study the wound process at the molecular level. In this vein, the development and implementation of biocompatible materials is an important trend in modern biopharmaceuticals [23, 24, 33].

The purpose is to analyze the scientific literature to learn about the structure and functions of this enzyme in various species of living organisms, as well as the possibilities of its use in industry and medicine. Goals: 1) to reveal the physiological role of TG in terms of the prospects of commercial application; 2) to reveal the existence of an evolutionary connection between microbial TG and TG of higher organisms; 3) to study the role of natural tissue TG in skin regeneration: in the papillary layer of the dermis and skin-epidermal junction; 4) to study the possibilities of TGs use in medicine.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Functions of the enzyme. Transglutaminases (TG) are a family of extremely widespread naturally occurring enzymes catalyzing 3 types of reactions: acyl transfer, the formation of covalent bonds between the amino acid residues of lysine and glutamine in proteins, and the deamination reaction. The covalent bonds formed by TG are resistant to proteolysis, and the protein polymers crosslinked by them are, as a rule, insoluble. These biological polymers are necessary for organisms to create stable structures in tissues [1, 2, 3, 8, 10, 31, 43]. Catalyzed TG reactions between different amine substrates take place in cells, carrying out a large number of physiological functions. The reaction proceeds in two stages: it begins with the formation of bound high-molecular protein aggregates, and then protein-polyamine conjugates are formed. They can further polymerize. TG catalytic reactions are usually irreversible and are

carefully regulated by various control mechanisms [43].

A large number of physiological functions in the body occurs when TG catalyzed reactions [49]. The physiological role of TG has aroused a keen interest of researchers in recent years in terms of the prospects of commercial application. According to the structure of the active center, TG is referred to the superfamily of papain-like cysteine proteases, their activity depends on the calcium concentration in the [9, 10, 11, 19, 43, 49].

The term "transglutaminase" was first introduced by D. Clarke et al. in 1959, when describing the enzyme system obtained from the guinea pig liver fraction; several enzyme substrates have been described, as well as factors affecting the activity, such as pH, temperatures, concentrations of inhibitors and activators [4, 6, 18]. In later studies on the stabilization of human fibrin monomers in the process of blood coagulation, the biochemical function of TG as a coagulation factor XIII [29] was described. Stabilization of fibrin is achieved by threading the protein strands through an acyl transfer reaction involving TG and the formation of an epsilon-gamma-glutamyl-lysine-isopeptide bond [18]. *Human transglutaminases.* Human TGs are monomers with a domain structure, the usual number of domains is four [18]. Factor XIII (F XIII) is a protransglutaminase, which has active and intracellular forms. Its plasma fraction is a tetramer of two potentially active (A) subunits and two regulatory subunit carriers (B), and the cell fraction is a dimer (FXIII_{A2}) [20]. Analysis of the amino acid sequences of different representatives of the TG family made it possible to reveal the high similarity of the structure of individual domains (the differences in the primary structure were revealed only at the N- and C-termini) [23]. This made it possible to characterize the structure of tissue TGs within the framework of the homologous model based on crystalline factor XIII [20].

TG participation (besides blood clotting) has been established in a wide range of physiological and biochemical processes: cell differentiation, growth, regulation of apoptosis rate, extracellular matrix formation, tissue integrity, cell adhesion, endocytosis, epidermal and hair cover stabilization, wound healing and angiogenesis [14, 15, 31, 43, 46]. A collection of known cofactors of TG and their substrates is available in the TRANSDB database. In humans, eight forms of TG are described, genes encoding these enzymes are mapped (Table 1).

Table 1: Brief characteristics of human TG

The name	Encoding genes (chromosome regions)	Localization	Main function	Symbol
blood coagulation factor XIII	F13A1, F13B (6p25-p24)	blood	blood clotting, thrombus formation	FXIII, factor XIII
TG of keratinocytes	14q11.2	skin	formation of the stratum corneum of the epidermis, development of the hair follicles	TG1, TG1
tissue TG	20q11.2-q12	all over the place	formation of extracellular matrix, wound healing, regulation of apoptosis	TG2, TG2
epidermal TG	20q12	skin	formation of the stratum corneum of the epidermis	TG3, TG3
Prostatic TG	3p22-p21.33	Prostate gland	regulation of spermatogenesis	TG4, TG4
TG X	15q15.2	skin	skin formation of the stratum corneum of the epidermis	TG5, TG5
TG Y	20q11-15	is not clear	is not clear	TG6, TG6
TG Z	15q15.2	testicles, lungs	is not clear	TG7, TG7

The great importance the TG of mammals and humans has for the regulation of reproduction and the formation of a skin barrier [33]. In the formation of the stratum corneum of the epidermis in the stage of terminal differentiation of keratinocytes, the covalent cross-linking of proteins under the cell membrane occurs with the help and successive co-operation of TG1, TG2 and TG5. Violation of their activity and coordinated action changes the normal structure of the skin [49].

Proteins with the activity similar to TG are found not only in mammals, but in representatives of a wide variety of taxa: microorganisms, plants, invertebrates, amphibians, fish and birds. In most cases, such proteins are significantly smaller than human, the shortest polypeptide chain (331 amino acid residues) is found in TG produced by the *Streptovorticillium mobaraense* bacterium. Microbial TGs (MTG) are of interest for practical use and have been extensively studied in representatives of various genera [31, 43]. The existence of an evolutionary connection between microbial TG and TG of higher organisms, a peculiar phylogenetic tree of TG from various sources, is shown that indicates that TG of animals and humans originated from TG bacteria [28, 30, 31, 32]. Investigation of the crystal structure of MTG revealed both differences and the possibility of convergent evolution of enzymes. Nevertheless, the catalytic triad of TG animals "Cys-His-Asp" is superimposed on "Cys-Asp-His" in the active center of MTG, and the similarity of the secondary structure of the environment of these residues and activation mechanisms indicates their functional relationship [49].

The use of transglutaminases. MTG in the molecular structure contains 11 alpha helices and 8 beta layers, it has a higher reactivity and broad substrate specificity for acyl residue donors, as well as lower deamidation activity compared to human TG. MTG are active at a pH of 4.5-8.0 (optimum 5.5-6.0) and a temperature range of +5 to +50 °C (optimum +40 °C) regardless of the concentration of calcium ions in the medium [31, 49], which is important from a practical point of view.

Biotechnologists have isolated a highly productive recombinant TG-synthesizing strain of *E. coli*. At present, relatively cheap MTGs are widely used in the food industry as safe technological agents [31]. TG is used to make products from fish mass, in sausage production, sausages to increase density, because promote the formation of protein-protein bonds and a protein network structure in which water and fat are retained. MTG catalyze the binding of any food protein, especially proteins of high glutamine content (wheat and soy proteins), casein and gelatin, used in the dairy and confectionery industries [31] are particularly suitable as substrates.

The use of MTG makes it possible to reduce the content of form-forming agents, products of chemical synthesis - carrageenans, phosphates, gums, emulsifiers in products. The MTG is characterized by storage stability, especially when carbohydrates and reduced glutathione are added, as well as protection from oxygen of air and other oxidants. A feature of these enzymes is rapid biodegradation [31].

Transglutaminases in medicine. The role of natural

tissue TG in skin regeneration was studied: in the papillary layer of the dermis and skin-epidermal junction, activity of TG was revealed, the potential substrate of which was defined as type VII collagen and fibronectin. An increase in its activity in paravulnary tissues on day 3 was detected immunologically in an experiment on rats. Participation of TG not only in the process of organization of the extracellular matrix, but also in the regulation of cytokine-associated inflammation and angiogenesis was shown [27]. What was the scientific rationale for using TG to suggest new methods for treating wounds and preventing the formation of pathological scars [17].

Factor XIII concentrate is used in medicine to treat its hereditary deficiency, Lucky-Lorand disease, autosomal recessive disease, which manifests itself as bleeding, poor wound healing and abnormal formation of postoperative scars. Its effective use in wound healing is described [50]. There are a number of expensive foreign preparations containing concentrate factor XIII - Berioplast Takeda (Japan), Corifact® (USA), Fibrogammin (Great Britain), Tretten® (Denmark), most of them are not included in the state drug register of the Russian Federation (<http://grls.rosminzdrav.ru/grls.aspx>).

Isolated coagulation factor XIII (concentrate) is not produced in Russia, and blood products (cryoprecipitate and fresh frozen plasma) are expensive and scarce, the spread of hematogenous infections also does not contribute to the development of methods for using them to treat wounds. It is extremely important to use a purified preparation of placental factor XIII and TG as a biological glue in plastic surgery, to treat fractures of bones and cartilage lesions. The disadvantage of drugs from serums and tissues is the high cost. It is currently more promising to use recombinant enzymes than tissue extracted from tissues [5, 18, 21, 22].

A new treatment approach, taking into account knowledge of the role of enzymes, is not only in the appointment of exogenous enzyme preparations, but also in modulating the expression of endogenous TG by specific inducers, such as retinoids. This method is considered as a strategic one in the treatment of skin diseases and a number of oncological diseases [9]. To use in surgery, adhesives containing tissue TG, gelatin or fibrinogen with the properties of natural biological glues, blood-restoring and early-insulating agents are suggested. The high potential of TG for medicine was also noted in the monograph published in Japan in 2016 "Transglutaminases: multiple

functional modifiers and targets for new drug discovery" [49].

A number of studies demonstrate that disturbances in the function of tissue TG in humans can contribute to the pathophysiology of inflammatory, autoimmune and degenerative diseases (celiac disease, herpetiform dermatitis, familial ataxia, prostate cancer, etc.) [7, 25, 33, 34]. Excessive activity of tissue TG and imbalance in their regulation can cause pathological scarring and organ sclerosis [40, 48]. However, they can participate in biological processes through actions not related to catalytic activity [29, 39, 41]. Until the mechanisms of participation of various forms of TG in the processes of cell differentiation and apoptosis are fully understood, the therapeutic potential of these enzymes should be evaluated with caution. In addition, the industrial isolation of tissue TG in quantities sufficient for widespread use for medical purposes seems to us rather complicated.

As can be seen, TG microbial origin is the most promising and interesting for the expansion of the possibilities of surgery and veterinary medicine in the field of wound healing. MTG are small in size, their activity is independent of calcium ions, they are stable during storage and at the same time are prone to rapid biodegradation [31, 42, 38]. The principle of their work ("cross-linking" the proteins of the intercellular matrix) suggests that the risk of immune reactions in their use is low.

The regeneration of the deep cut and burning wounds of the skin after different variants of local therapy. Wound healing is an urgent medical problem, where closure of wounds (wall convergence) by means of seams and adhesives is of primary importance, and the use of wound healing agents [17, 26, 27, 44, 45]. Despite the abundance and variety of drugs available on the pharmaceutical market for local therapy of wound defects of various etiologies, the desired degree of reparative effect has not yet been achieved. Existing standards of pharmacotherapy of wounds do not satisfy both the effectiveness of treatment and the cost of achieving the final result. In surgery, at the initial stages of the wound process, simple antiseptics and wound-healing ointments are used ("Solcoseryl" and "Metuluracil" are the leaders). The modern level of development of science allowed us to study the wound process at the molecular level. In this vein, the development and implementation of biocompatible materials is an important trend in modern biopharmaceuticals. At present, much attention is paid to the mechanisms of the organization of wound contents and tissue matrix reformatting. TG enzymes (serum and tissue) that are capable of forming

proteolysis-resistant cross-linking between extracellular matrix proteins [31, 35, 36, 43] are involved in these processes. Drugs of human serum TG in Russia, like all blood products, are produced and used in a limited way. TG mammals and humans are autoantigens and may be associated with the pathogenesis of certain diseases [6, 24, 33, 47].

At the same time, inexpensive MTGs are widely used in the industry as safe technological agents [31, 51-53]. TG of microbial origin, unlike oligomeric TGs of mammals and humans, are small single-chain proteins, their activity does not depend on the concentration of calcium ions, they are stable at storage and, at the same time, they are characterized by rapid biodegradation.

The idea of creating a new preparation (ointment) containing microbial TG in combination with traditional phytopreparations and active components that affect various targets of the pathological process in tissue damage, and determined the purpose and objectives of our study. On this basis, our work was planned: «The regeneration of the deep cut and burning wounds of the skin after different variants of local therapy». Deep cut wounds and singes are one of the most common injuries in accidents and still remain a global public health problem. Despite many successes in wound therapy, there is still a need to search and develop new medicines for their local treatment. The purpose is to determine the possibilities of using local therapy with enzyme microbial transglutaminase (MTG) with an auxiliary experimental substance of the author's herbal ointment in the modeling of full-bladed cut wounds based on the study of the morphogenesis of skin regeneration processes. Goals: 1) to reveal the histological and immunohistochemical features of the regeneration of deep cut wounds in white rats under the influence of transglutaminase enzyme in various concentrations; 2) to study the features of the morphogenesis of skin regeneration in the modeling of III degree burn wounds under conditions of local therapy with microbial transglutaminase with an auxiliary experimental substance of author's phytoointment.

We investigated the dynamics of the skin regenerative processes in the group without treatment, after using the common medicine Solcoseryl and after application of the author's technique – the use of the ointment or its combinations with the enzyme MTG of various concentrations. The set of morphological techniques for the study the skin structure on the level of organ, tissue, cells and subcellular organization were used in

the experiment on 150 white mice males. The methods included: macroscopic method for describing and measuring of the size of lesions; histological methods for light-optical level – a qualitative assessment of the morphologic changes of the skin; the method of transmission electron microscopy - to identify ultrastructural transformation of different cells of the epidermis and dermis; immunohistochemical - to assess the expression of markers of the regenerative process (studies with markers Ki-67, CD68 and CD138 were carried out).

The most effective medicine for the healing of the full-thickness cut wounds on the results of the visual assessment and histological examination is the MTG at a concentration of 0.1%, proved by the evidence of the stop of the bleeding and the formation of the fibrin clot 3 times faster than in other experimental and control groups; the early onset of epithelialization on the 3-d day of the experiment, the final completion of the regenerative processes to the 10-th day, that indicated the prospects of the transglutaminase using in surgery and aesthetic medicine. Histological examination showed the completion of regenerative processes in groups with the application of phytoointment with the MTG enzyme already on the seventh postoperative day, in the presence of increased proliferative activity of the epidermocytes. MTG initiates a rapid sequential phase change of the regenerative process and synchronous recovery of epithelial and stromal components. In early stage of healing of cut wounds, MTG helps to fill the defect with a dense fibrin clot, providing an isolating antiseptic effect and subsequently intensifying the formation of connective tissue scar [54-57].

Healing of third degree burn wounds with the use of the ointment "Solcoseryl" is characterized by different obtained results. Epithelialization of the wound surface in most of cases occurs by primary tension without scar formation and terminates on average by the 21-st day, at the same time 25% of animals showed the secondary tension healing with the formation of coarse-fibrous scar tissue.

The histological and immunohistochemical examination of skin biopsies of rats with Ki-67, CD68 and CD138 markers during the healing of burn wounds allowed the morphogenetic characteristics of the regeneration process to be dynamically changed depending on the type of local wound therapy. Intensification of the wound surface healing process occurred in the group with a local application of microbial transglutaminase 0.03% (peak values on

day 3 CD68+ - 42.1 ± 0.3 , $p < 0.05$), resulting in an increase in reactivity of the stromal component followed by acceleration by formation and remodeling of connective tissue scar (diffuse stromal and cytoplasmic reaction of the syndecan-1/CD138 marker with negative membrane expression) and complete epithelialization already by 10 days of the experiment ($Ki67 + -3.3 \pm 0.3$, $p < 0.05$). The use of 0.1% microbial transglutaminase substance is justified in the first three days for the prevention of secondary bacterial contamination of the wound surface (as a biologically intact means of isolating the lesion) [54-57].

The use of an innovative technique for local treatment of deep cut wounds of the skin with an enzyme microbial transglutaminase with an auxiliary experimental substance of the author's herbal ointment is characterized by an early onset of epithelialization, which indicates the prospects of transglutaminases in surgery and aesthetic medicine. At the same time, the mechanisms of reparation should be further investigated in a series of clinical trials.

CONCLUSION:

Analyzing the literature we concluded that much attention is paid to the mechanisms of the organization of wound contents and tissue matrix reformatting.

TG enzymes (serum and tissue) that are capable of forming proteolysis-resistant cross-linking between extracellular matrix proteins are involved in these processes.

Drugs of human serum TG in Russia, like all blood products, are produced and used in a limited way. TG mammals and humans are autoantigens and may be associated with the pathogenesis of certain diseases.

TG microbial origin is the most promising and interesting for the expansion of the possibilities of surgery and veterinary medicine in the field of wound healing. MTG are small in size. The principle of their work ("cross-linking" the proteins of the intercellular matrix) suggests that the risk of immune reactions in their use is low.

Inexpensive MTGs are widely used in the industry as safe technological agents. TG of microbial origin, unlike oligomeric TGs of mammals and humans, are small single-chain proteins, their activity does not depend on the concentration of calcium ions, they are stable at storage and, at the same time, they are characterized by rapid biodegradation.

The idea of creating a new preparation (ointment) containing microbial TG in combination with traditional phytopreparations and active components that affect various targets of the pathological process

in tissue damage, and determined the purpose and objectives of our study. At the same time, the mechanisms of reparation should be further investigated in a series of clinical trials.

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